

Learning from history: Jens Høyrup on mathematics, education, and society

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I summarize just a few themes from the writings of the historian/anthropologist of mathematics, Jens Høyrup, that relate to the work of MES. His sheer hard work in striving to understand and explain the mathematical practices of others across millennia and multiple cultures, always in relation to sociopolitical contexts, underpins his ability to convey, to those prepared to make the effort, the relevance of the history of pre- and early modern mathematical practices to perennial issues in mathematics education.

A confession and an enigma

To begin with a confession, I have only recently become aware of how important Jens Høyrup is to our field. My interest was aroused in the last couple of years because of searching for writings on mathematics and war, which took me to Booß-Bavnbeek and Høyrup (2003). Since then, I have begun to appreciate the measure, number, and weight of his writings, almost invariably available online (and mostly in English, which raises an important point about the distorting effect of the hegemony of English in our field, that space restrictions preclude me addressing) – notably, Høyrup (2020). Høyrup (2019) contains a small selection of his essays (a mere 31). Now that I have become aware of the importance of his work, I find it an enigma that it is so little recognized in our field, in particular the MES corner of it. Using the search specification “word: Høyrup, author: X” within Google Scholar, with X ranging over many obvious names, yields very little. In what follows, be assured that I am only scratching the surface.

History of mathematics is demanding work

Historians in general, and historians of mathematics in very specific ways, have to struggle with attempting to understand “the Other” from within the worldview of their own cultural matrix and personal history. It is a problem shared, in varying ways, by child psychologists, anthropologists, therapists, translators, and others, one that has been extensively debated within Ethnomathematics in particular.

Writing in the context of Chinese culture, but with general relevance, Cullen (2009, p. 592) cautioned against:

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[...] the idea that there is *a priori* a universal ahistorical cross-cultural “natural kind” called “mathematics” that can simply be located and studied once one can penetrate the linguistic barrier to see what it is called in Chinese, and on which one can simply impose all the structures and expectations that a modern person finds in the subject called “mathematics” in twenty-first-century English.

Reading Høystrup, it is obvious how painstakingly he applied principles of close reading and structural analysis informed by his study of literary theory. The following quotation is offered as simply one illustration, related to an interest of mine, namely multiplication and division as models for situations, emphasizing distinctions such as the effects of the kinds of numbers and quantities involved, and the differences between “symmetric” and “asymmetric” cases (Greer, 1992; and see Hofstadter & Sander, 2013, Chapter 7 for an insightful discussion):

The four operations originally interpreted as multiplications are:

- steps of [...] a multiplication of pure number by pure number;
- to raise [...] originally used in volume calculation, where the base is “raised” to the default height of one cubit to the real height, and then transferred metaphorically to other calculations of concrete magnitudes by multiplication;
- to make [two segments] hold, name “hold” a rectangle [...] This is just no genuine multiplication but a construction, mostly implying, however, the determination of the resulting area;
- to repeat or repeat until n [...] a concrete doubling (e.g., of a right triangle into a rectangle) or n -doubling (n being sufficiently small to be intuitively graspable, $a \leq n \leq 9$).

(Høystrup, 2010, p. 6)

(His analysis of the diversity of usages for the four arithmetical operations strikingly echoes that of Urton, 1997, for Quechua mathematics). Note that technical details of transliteration are omitted in the above; the quotation is followed by interpretations of terms used and suggested inferences as to the cognitive operations involved. The complexities of translation, such as the principle of “conformal translation” that he pioneered can only be hinted at here; the following quotation makes a clear point:

The technical meaning of the Babylonian terms has to be learned from their use, not imported from a different conceptual structure – who would get the idea to translate technical texts from the early eighteenth century using terms like oxygen, hydrogen, etc.? (Høystrup, 2010, p. 6, footnote).

His precision and the care that he takes with his analyses puts Høystrup in a strong position to critique less conscientious historians, particularly those relying on dated secondary sources, and he pulls no punches in this regard. Any connoisseur of long-drawn-out complex exegetical disputes would enjoy Høystrup (2017a).

On Ethnomathematics

In the preface to Høystrup (1994, p. xi) (and earlier in Høystrup, 1980) he explains his choice of the term “anthropology of mathematics” to characterize his approach:

[...] a term which suggested neither crushing of the socially and historically particular nor the oblivion of the search for possible more general structures: a term which neither implied that the history of mathematics was nothing but the gradual but unilinear discovery of ever-existing Platonic truths nor ... a random walk [among] an infinity of possible systems of belief. A term, finally, which involved the importance of cross-cultural comparisons.

Like anthropology, cognitive psychology, and other fields, history of mathematics (in the European and extended-European context) is striving to emerge from its colonial and racist roots. In particular, one focus of Ethnomathematics is creating a counter-narrative to the Eurocentric myth (Høyrup, 1992). Morris Kline provided the easiest of targets when he wrote:

Mathematics is a living plant [that] finally secured a firm grip on life in the highly congenial soil of Greece and waxed strong for a brief period. In this period it produced one perfect flower, Euclidean geometry. The buds of other flowers opened slightly [...] but these flowers withered with the decline of Greek civilization, and the plant remained dormant for one thousand years. Such was the state of mathematics when the plant was transported to Europe proper and once more embedded in fertile soil. (Kline, 1953, p. 27)

(See also Chemla, 2012). Commenting on the writing of Kline and two others, Høyrup (2010, p. 4) concluded that the other two interpreted Babylonian texts by “translating” them into what they took to be the contemporary equivalents, while Kline found in them something that he did not consider counted as mathematics.

The implied message (probably resulting because it is the implicit starting point for all three) is the same: there is only one kind of mathematics: *ours*.

He located the counter-narrative within the context of imperialism and white supremacy in the unforgettably succinct and incisive phrase “the ideological shroud assigning the right to conquer and kill in the name of moral superiority” (Høyrup, 2020, p. 8). Just as powerfully, throughout his work, he draws attention to the cultural violence done in the name of intellectual superiority. At the same time, let me note, in passing, that his unflinching gaze distances him from any oversentimental notions about absence of brutality and injustice in other cultures (e.g., Chapter 24 in Høyrup, 2019, pp. 661–688).

With his penchant for terminological exactitude, he (very necessarily) problematizes terms such as “Western” and “non-Western” (2020, p. 8), and how about this for a footnote? (Høyrup, 2018, p. 7):

The ancient Greeks were not Europeans. They would certainly have been no more pleased by being lumped together with Illyrian, Italic, Iberian, Gallic or Germanic barbarians than a Japanese teacher of mine when the Apartheid regime in South Africa decided in the late 1960s to consider Japanese “white by honour”.

He aligns with d’Ambrosio’s definition of Ethnomathematics as the study of the mathematical practices of cultural groups of all kinds (including academic mathematicians). And he pointed out that “Ethnomathematics”, no less than “mathematics” is “*our* concept” (Høyrup, 1994, p. 67).

Of particular interest is his discussion of the relationships between aspects of “decoration, art, and structural inquiry” (Høyrup, 2000) that he approaches within the framework of a

“hermeneutics of non-verbal expression” (p. 160 in Høyrup, 2019), relating to the problem of “the Other” mentioned above. He concludes:

The moral of the present tale is, firstly, that we should be careful not to extrapolate from *every* piece of geometrical decoration to such extensive symmetries which may be superimposed on its pattern but which are not needed to explain it... secondly, that no necessity leads from an *aesthetics of forms* to *formal investigation of forms*, nor from *formal investigation of forms* to *integration with mensurational geometry* or *into mathematics as a broader endeavour* (Høyrup, 2000, pp. 202–203 in Høyrup, 2019).

Here I take it that he is arguing that rather than a casual assumption that mathematics may be read into *any* aesthetic effort, a close study of each case is required. Thus, in his review of Gerdes (1994), he states that:

All the examples explored by Gerdes (and sub-Saharan geometrical decoration in broad average as far as the reviewer is aware) belong to the [...] type [which] bears witness of deliberate explorations of symmetries and other formalizeable properties of figures (Høyrup, 1996, p. 203 in Høyrup, 2019).

(A fascinating modern example that I merely mention is that of Escher, how he related his art to mathematics, and his interactions with mathematicians, including Polya and Penrose; with a little online research, the interested reader will be able to find recent documentaries on the subject.)

Mathematics and the state

Høyrup (2009) asserts that mathematics is not generally implicated in the formation of “pristine” states (which I take to mean states in the process of initial formation), an exception being Mesopotamia of the late fourth millennium, when a system of accounting was instrumental in the emergence of the state and, conversely, the emergent system of mathematics was intimately bound up with its administrative role. Urton (2009, pp. 28–29) discusses similar issues in three contexts relating to: “mathematical philosophies and concepts of authority in the West” prior to invasion of the New World, including the rise of double entry bookkeeping; khipu record-keeping in the Inka empire; the uneven encounter between the two systems.

In 1800, Napoleon wrote that:

The advancement and perfection of mathematics are immediately connected with the prosperity of the state.

and, generally:

The functioning of the modern state presupposes a variety of mathematical technologies – accounting, statistics, and much more. Mathematics, on its part needs the institutions of the state (schools, universities, research institutions, etc.) to secure financing, recruitment and the rearing of competence. (Høyrup, 2009, p. 635 in Høyrup, 2019)

Hacking (1990) has documented, in Høyrupian detail, the ways in which the formal mathematics of probability and statistics developed within socio-political contexts, in close

relationship to changing views of the nature of humans, and in the service of states. In a rare overtly political statement, he trenchantly observed that:

We obtain data about a governed class whose deportment is offensive, and then attempt to alter what we guess are relevant conditions of that class in order to change the laws of statistics that the class obeys (Hacking, 1990, p. 119)

Generally, the mathematical establishment in the United States – in particular, but by no means solely – is complicit with the political and military establishments in failing to address the several crises facing humanity. As Davis and Hersh (1986, p. 267) put it, “nuclear weapons mathematics is an accepted component of American mathematics life”. Writing with Booß-Bavnbek in 1984 (reprinted in Høyrup, 1994, p. 225), Høyrup put involvement of the sciences with war next only to “the responsibility of the sciences for engendering the ecological crisis”. The COVID-19 pandemic continues. And we may add global manifestations of resurgent white supremacy, accelerating wealth inequality, and the effects of antisocial media in destroying any viable notion of truth.

Supra-utilitarian, “recreational”, and useless mathematics

Høyrup also makes abundantly clear that as people developed mathematical practices, essentially contemporaneously with the rise of civilization, such practices soon transcended the practical demands for surviving and then thriving. He also describes how pervasive is “recreational mathematics” and clarifies the uses for which such puzzles were developed. The mass and consistency of such “riddles” and “puzzles” across millennia and much of the globe is apparent in the enormous collection of sources compiled by David Singmaster. Of immediate relevance to contemporary education, in my view, is the class of problems that could be described as “only to be found within school mathematics”, including problems using unnaturally “nice” numbers or absurdly high numbers. Indeed, he comments that examples which serve to show that a method “may be used for *any* problem of a similar structure, not just for trite commercial calculation” and that such problems pass “imperceptibly into general school mathematics” (Høyrup, 1994, p. 28).

As one who has questioned the need for “algebra for all” (Greer, 2008), and, in particular, wondered why quadratic equations enjoy such prominence in mathematical curricula, I was intrigued to read the following (Høyrup, 2013, p. 7):

Many students will certainly be astonished to discover that even their teachers do not know why second-degree equations are solved. Students as well as teachers will be no less surprised that such equations have been taught since 1800 BCE without any possible external reference point for the students [...].

Styles of mathematical reasoning

While Hacking (2016) refers to six styles of scientific reasoning that have characterized science in Europe, namely mathematical, experimental exploration, hypothetical modelling, probabilistic, taxonomic, and historico-genetic, it is equally possible to distinguish different styles of reasoning within mathematics. At a very general level, Raju (2007, p. 413) argues

that within European mathematics there are two main streams. From Greece and Egypt came a mathematics that was spiritual, anti-empirical, proof-oriented, and explicitly religious; from India, via Arabs, a mathematics that was pro-empirical and calculation-oriented, with practical objectives. For a different take on “style” that emphasizes “ways of writing” rather than shared epistemologies see Rabouin (2017).

A great deal of Høyrup’s analysis of Old Babylonian mathematics is concerned with establishing the styles of reasoning that underlay their algebra, its relationship to geometry, and the relation of their “geometrical algebra” to that of the Greeks (Høyrup, 2005). He declares unequivocally that:

It is therefore to be expected that mathematics teaching in any mathematical culture which went beyond mere routine [...] did include appeals to reason – whether naive or critical, and whether in Greek style (or that dubious reading of the Greek style in which we project ourselves) is a different matter. If we cannot find traces of this reasoning in extant sources we may safely conclude that this is due, *either* to failing understanding of the sources on our part, *or* to the insufficiency of extant sources as mirrors of educational practice. *Tertium non datur.* (Høyrup, 2019, p. 560).

What is mathematics? (Høyrup, 2017b)

I suggest a fundamental shift from asking about mathematics as some kind of entity to asking about the uses of the word and about the families of practices in which it may be said to be implicated (clearly that is closely related to the definition of Ethnomathematics as the study of the mathematics of cultural groups, including academics). In similar spirit, Harouni (2015) referred to categories of mathematics that he labels commercial-administrative, philosophical, artisanal, and social-analytic.

The title of Høyrup’s (2019) selected essays refers to “mathematical practice”. A book could be written just on the usages of singular and plural nouns in discussions of “mathematics”, starting with that word itself in many languages (for example, Bourbaki used “mathématique” instead of the usual French plural form to proclaim its belief in the unity of mathematics). However, elsewhere he wrote that (1994, p. 67):

[...] we have a cluster of indubitably mathematical practices, disciplines, and techniques, cohering through shared use or investigation of abstract, more or less generalized number or space or of other abstract structures.

A closely related question is: “Who is a mathematician?” (Høyrup, 2003). Again, Cullen (2009, p. 593) clarifies with the questions:

[...] was there a self-conscious and publicly recognized group of people in ancient China with a family resemblance to what would be called nowadays “mathematicians”? What did these people call themselves? What did they consider their defining skill-set, or their common obsession to be?

(and similar warnings certainly apply to “schools” and “teachers”).

Dialectical processes

I have developed an aversion to binary questions such as “Is mathematics discovered or invented?”. It is safest to explore the terrain with a dialectical mine detector. For example, Høyrup (2002, p. 404) states:

In mathematics as elsewhere, the expansion of knowledge is a dialectical process where neither naive creativity nor critical consolidation can function alone, each of them establishing that the other may become operative,

which resonates with the declaration by Hacking (2016, p. 13) that “the history of mathematics is one of diversity and unification”. Further, he emphasizes that the historian can describe developments internal to a discipline (such as mathematics) and also external drivers but that such descriptions lack explanatory capability “as long as no dialectical synthesis takes place” (Høyrup 1994, p. xiii). For a mathematician’s take on the internal/external interplay on developments within mathematics and mathematics education in the 20th century, see Mandelbrot (1994).

To make my final point that history also includes the future, I refer to Freudenthal on Piaget’s supposed discovery of a direct correspondence between his hypothetical roots of mathematical cognition and Bourbaki’s “mother structures”:

Piaget is not a mathematician, so he could not know how unreliable mathematical system builders are [...] Mathematics is never finished – anyone who worships a certain system of mathematics should take heed of this advice. (Freudenthal, 1973, p. 46)

Or, as Høyrup (1995, p. 5, footnote 4) put it:

No critique is ever definitive. What seemed at one moment to be an absolute underpinning [...] turns out with historical insight to make other “naïve” presuppositions which in their turn can be “criticized”.

Final comments

Philosophers, like most other people who think about it at all, tend to take “mathematics” for granted. (Hacking, 2014, p. 41)

The study of history of mathematics offers an extremely effective remedy. And, in relation to education, many have made the essential point that

school is seen as a magical shortcut that allows ideas arduously developed by humanity over thousands of years to be transmitted in a few years to a random human being (Hofstadter & Sander, 2013, p. 391)

Further, Høyrup so clearly demonstrates the complexity of conceptual change and illustrates how analysing the epistemological crises of the past and how they were addressed could inform contemporary teaching.

The characterization of much mathematics as supra-utilitarian or useless reflects the imbalance (in my opinion) pervasive in mathematics education whereby curricula, pedagogy,

and assessment cater more for the preparation and selection of future mathematics students, rather than being guided by considerations of usefulness for the general population. This imbalance is, to a considerable extent, influenced by the desire of mathematicians to perpetuate their species, enabled by what could be termed the unreasonable political effectiveness of “mathematics” as a term of propaganda.

His work bears heavily, in my judgment, on the current ideological fault line in global mathematics education between homogenization and diversity in all its forms, including styles of reasoning. In the spirit of Ethnomathematics, he shows how diversity is manifest in all families of practices involving mathematics, with the notable, and arguably unfortunate, exception of school mathematics.

A partial explanation for the enigma to which I refer at the beginning is that Høystrup presents so much in the form of meticulous detail (“the socially and historically particular” in the quotation above about anthropology of mathematics) that a little work is necessary to find the “more general structures” (same quotation). I assert that such work is richly awarded; for me, the points made above have been greatly reinforced by reading him. As someone who needs to eke out his remaining intellectual resources, “discovering” Høystrup at my age is a blessing and a curse. To younger colleagues, I urge you to start serious study now of this remarkable scholar’s work.

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